

Access, Equity, and Accountability: Unpacking the Meaning of 'High-Quality' in Perkins V CTE Plans

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Abstract

This roundtable presentation explores how equity and access are represented in state-level definitions of “high-quality” postsecondary Career and Technical Education (CTE) programs under Perkins V. Guided by the Access and Equity element of the ACTE High-Quality CTE Program of Study Framework, the study uses qualitative content analysis to examine 2024–2027 Perkins V state plans. Specifically, it identifies how frequently and substantively these plans address special populations and equity-related outcomes. Preliminary findings from 15 state plans reveal significant variability in attention to equity, with few states explicitly linking access for special populations to accountability measures used to define high-quality CTE programs.

Introduction

As Career and Technical Education (CTE) continues to gain national momentum as a strategy for preparing students for postsecondary success and workforce participation, there is an increasing demand for frameworks that guide and evaluate program quality. The Association for Career and Technical Education (ACTE) addressed this need by developing the *High-Quality CTE Program of Study Framework* (Imperatore & Hyslop, 2018), which identifies 12 interrelated elements that comprise a high-quality CTE program. These elements include rigorous, standards-aligned curriculum, meaningful work-based learning experiences, robust industry partnerships, and equitable access for all learners. The framework aligns closely with the goals of the Strengthening Career and Technical Education for the 21st Century Act (Perkins V), which emphasizes both performance accountability and equitable access to high-quality programs (U.S. Department of Education, 2018). As such, the ACTE framework has become an accepted tool for guiding program improvement and ensuring alignment with federal policy goals.

A critical yet under-examined component of the ACTE framework is the element of Access and Equity (Dolfi, 2022). This component calls for intentional strategies to support historically marginalized students, including women in non-traditional fields, students with disabilities, and individuals from economically disadvantaged backgrounds (Imperatore & Hyslop, 2018). To support this need, ACTE developed an online repository of resources to aid CTE practitioners in supporting the success of special populations. Additionally, in 2021, ACTE published a follow-up to their high-quality framework to support states in developing their Perkins V comprehensive local needs assessment, entitled “Quality CTE Program of Study Framework Self-evaluation: A Tool

for the Perkins V Comprehensive Local Needs Assessment,” in which the requirements for states to address plans both for high-quality and special populations, among other requirements (ACTE, 2021).

As states implement their Perkins V plans, questions emerge about how consistently and equitably these principles are applied, particularly when “high-quality” is defined in terms of labor market outcomes, credential attainment, and post-program earnings. This study utilizes the ACTE (Imperatore & Hyslop, 2018) framework’s Access and Equity element as a lens to examine how state Perkins V plans define, apply, and potentially problematize the designation of “high-quality” CTE in ways that may shape both opportunities and exclusions.

Conceptual Framework/Theoretical Framework

The ACTE *High-Quality CTE Program of Study Framework* (Imperatore & Hyslop, 2018) serves as a comprehensive guide for evaluating the quality and impact of CTE programs across the United States. Developed to support continuous improvement and consistency in CTE program delivery, the framework outlines 12 key elements of high-quality CTE, encompassing standards-aligned curriculum, work-based learning, program promotion, and accountability. Each element includes a set of criteria and quality indicators to help educators, administrators, and policymakers assess the extent to which CTE programs are effectively preparing students for college and careers. The framework emphasizes the need for data-driven decision-making, student-centered instruction, and alignment with labor market demands, principles that mirror the priorities embedded in Perkins V legislation.

A critical element of the ACTE framework, particularly relevant to this study, is the Access and Equity indicator. This element emphasizes the importance of providing equitable access to high-quality CTE programs for all learners, particularly those from historically marginalized groups (Institute for Research on Poverty, 2019; Smith, 2019). The framework calls for proactive recruitment of underrepresented populations, including women in non-traditional fields, racial and ethnic minorities, students with disabilities, and individuals from economically disadvantaged backgrounds. High-quality CTE programs, according to this element, not only remove barriers to participation but also actively foster inclusive learning environments through “non-discriminatory” instruction, targeted support services, and intentional outreach efforts. For the present study, this element provides a crucial lens through which to analyze how Perkins V state plans conceptualize and implement equitable access, as well as how indicators of quality might either support or inadvertently disadvantage programs serving diverse learner populations. By applying this framework, researchers can better determine the degree to which state-defined “high-quality” CTE programs prioritize both performance outcomes and equitable student representation.

Purpose and Research Questions

This roundtable presentation focuses on the initial stage of inquiry into the intersection of high-quality postsecondary CTE programming and equitable access and outcomes for special populations as defined by Perkins V.

The broader research study will address the following Research Questions:

1. To what extent do states' 2024-27 Perkins V plans mention intentions related to access and outcomes for special populations?
2. Do postsecondary CTE programs in states with Perkins V plans that explicitly prioritize enrollment of special populations enroll higher percentages of students from those groups (e.g., women, racial/ethnic minorities, economically disadvantaged students, students with disabilities, historically underrepresented groups) compared to states with more general or limited references to special populations?
3. Do the indicators and metrics used to evaluate CTE program quality (e.g., earnings, in-demand occupations, credential attainment) unintentionally disadvantage programs with higher participation rates from women or underrepresented populations?

The objective of this roundtable presentation is to address Research Question 1 by identifying whether and how current state Perkins plans include intentions related to access and outcomes for special populations as outlined in Perkins V legislation. As such, the discussion of Methods and initial findings is intentionally limited to Research Question 1.

Methods

Study Design

To address Research Question 1, the researchers employed a qualitative content analysis approach to systematically review Perkins V state plans from multiple U.S. states. The goal is to identify and analyze the presence, definitions, and contextual usage of key terminology and themes related to CTE implementation under Perkins V legislation. These findings will inform the selection of states for deeper analysis in subsequent phases addressing Research Questions 2 and 3. This roundtable presentation will focus on addressing Research Question 1.

Data Sources

The primary data consists of publicly available Perkins V state plans obtained by the researchers from each state's official education department website. This review was conducted from February through May 2025. Typically, state plans can also be found on the Perkins Collaborative Resource Network in the U.S. Department of Education's Office of Career, Technical, and Adult Education resources portal. However, the site was currently under construction during the research phase.

To conduct a comprehensive and representative analysis of how states mention intentions related to access and outcomes for special populations, a set of preliminary selection criteria was established to guide the inclusion of state plans in this study. The criteria were designed to ensure that the selected states provided accessible, detailed, and current documentation aligned with the study's priorities.

1. Public Availability of the Perkins V State Plan

The first criterion required that the state's updated 2024-2027 Perkins V plan be publicly available online on the state's Department of Education. Thirty-three states with

inaccessible or outdated plans were excluded from the initial review phase. For example, the fiscal year 2020-23 plan may only have been on the website rather than the updated and approved 2024-27 plan.

2. Inclusion of Relevant Search Terms and Thematic Content

State plans that met criterion 1 then underwent a preliminary keyword scan to determine whether it included meaningful references to core terms central to this study: "high-quality," "high-demand," "labor market alignment," "special populations," "non-traditional fields," "gender equity," "economic mobility," and "occupational segregation." States that did not address a sufficient number of these themes in the body of their plan or appendices were not selected for full analysis, as the absence of this information would not support the study's research questions.

3. Presence of an Identifiable State-Level Contact

To ensure the possibility of follow-up communication or clarification, plans were prioritized if they identified a state CTE director or designated Perkins coordinator along with accurate contact information (e.g., email address, phone number, or official title). The inclusion of a named official will allow researchers the option of triangulating document data with expert insight if needed.

States meeting all three criteria were advanced to the coding and full content analysis phase. This structured approach helped ensure the sample included diverse state contexts while maintaining methodological consistency and data integrity.

Data Collection and Analysis Procedures

A deductive coding process was first applied using predefined categories aligned with ACTE's Access and Equity indicators, including: (a) recruitment and outreach to underrepresented groups, (b) removal of barriers to participation, (c) supports and accommodations for special populations, and (d) equity-focused evaluation measures.

Using keyword searches within electronic copies of state plans; researchers identified relevant sections addressing each term or theme. Text excerpts were extracted and organized by category. The analysis involved:

1. Identifying explicit definitions of terms such as "high-quality" and "high-demand."
2. Examining how labor market data and employment information were integrated into program planning.
3. Reviewing descriptions of special populations.
4. Investigating language related to gender equity, women's participation, and non-traditional fields.
5. Exploring references to economic mobility and occupational segregation as outcomes or concerns.
6. Analyzing procedures for conducting the Comprehensive Local Needs Assessment.
7. Documenting strategies for preparing special populations for competitive, integrated employment in high-skill, high-wage, or in-demand occupations.

Three researchers independently coded the data to ensure reliability. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion and consensus.

Ethical Considerations

As the study analyzed publicly available policy documents, it did not require Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval.

Preliminary Findings

To date, the research team has reviewed all 50 states' official Departments of Education websites to identify publicly available and approved 2024–2027 Perkins V state plans. At the time of this proposal, 18 state plans had been identified as publicly accessible and eligible for preliminary analysis based on the availability of full plan documentation.

Using the predefined key terms and selection criteria outlined above, 15 of the 18 identified state plans were found to include meaningful references to equity-related concepts central to this study (Criterion 2) and to identify a designated state-level contact for Perkins V implementation (Criterion 3). These plans were therefore included in the preliminary analysis. State plans that did not sufficiently address these core themes within the main body of the document or supporting appendices were excluded from full analysis, as the absence of this information limited their relevance to the study's research questions.

Collectively, these preliminary findings indicate substantial variation in how states articulate equity and access for special populations within their Perkins V state plans, underscoring the need for deeper analysis of how high-quality CTE programs of study are defined and operationalized across states. Taken together, the findings suggest an overarching trend in which high-quality CTE is frequently defined without explicit alignment to performance accountability measures that address equitable access, participation, and success for special populations. This initial screening and analysis phase establishes a critical foundation for subsequent phases of the study, which will further examine how state-level policy language aligns with accountability frameworks, implementation strategies, and postsecondary CTE access and outcomes for historically underserved learners as required under Perkins V.

Delimitations

The data sources for this study are limited to state Perkins V plans that are findable on official Department of Education websites by state. State plans that have not been published or approved are ineligible for inclusion. This study does not assess local implementation fidelity or student-level outcomes, which will be addressed in future phases of the research.

Implications for Future Research

As an initial phase of a broader, multi-stage research agenda, the findings presented in this roundtable serve as a foundation for examining how state-level policy definitions of “high-quality” CTE shape access, participation, and outcomes for special populations. By documenting the variability in how equity is articulated within 2024–

2027 Perkins V state plans, this study establishes a necessary baseline for subsequent analyses that move beyond policy language to examine implementation and outcomes.

Future phases of this project will build directly on these preliminary findings by exploring whether states that more explicitly integrate equity and special population access into their definitions of high-quality CTE demonstrate different enrollment patterns and outcomes at the postsecondary level. Specifically, planned analyses will examine the relationship between equity-oriented state plan language and student participation rates among women, racial and ethnic minorities, students with disabilities, and economically disadvantaged learners. This next phase is critical for assessing whether rhetorical commitments to equity translate into measurable differences in access and representation.

In addition, future research will investigate whether commonly used indicators of CTE program quality, such as credential attainment, earnings outcomes, and alignment with in-demand occupations, may unintentionally disadvantage programs that serve higher proportions of special populations. By linking policy definitions, performance metrics, and enrollment data, the broader study aims to illuminate potential tensions between accountability frameworks and equity goals embedded within Perkins V. Collectively, this line of inquiry seeks to inform more coherent, equity-centered approaches to defining and evaluating high-quality CTE programs in future state planning cycles and federal policy discussions.

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